

Knowledge, Attitudes And Practices of Livestock Farmers And Slaughter Slab Workers Regarding Hides And Skins Quality in Mbarara District, Uganda

Ambrose ARIHO¹, Robert TWINAMATSİKO^{2*}, John Patrick MUTAGUBYA³, Gabriel TUMWINE⁴, Simpson Sufficient BESİGYE⁵, Lydia NAMUKOMAZİ⁶

^{1,2}Department of Livestock and Industrial Resources, Makerere University, UGANDA

³Department of Agricultural and Environmental Sciences, University of Saint Joseph Mbarara, UGANDA

⁴Department of Biomolecular Resources & Biolab Sciences, Makerere University, UGANDA

⁵Faculty of Apparel, Bahir Dar University, ETHIOPIA

⁶Africa Institute for Strategic Animal Resource Services and Development (AFRISA), Makerere University, UGANDA

¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-4035-3132>,

²<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-6499-4919>,

³<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-3516-2519>,

⁴<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-5869-7837>,

⁵<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4249-1114>,

⁶<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-4587-8515>

Corresponding author: roberttwina@yahoo.com

Research Article

ABSTRACT

Article History:

Received: 13 June 2025

Accepted: 13 March 2026

Published online: 25 May 2026

Keywords:

Animal Husbandry Practices

Hides and Skins Defects

Leather Quality

Improvement

Leather Value Chain

Hides and skins are valuable by-products of the livestock industry and serve as raw materials for leather production and other applications. However, their quality and economic value vary significantly due to factors such as animal breed, management practices, and stakeholder knowledge. This study assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of livestock farmers and slaughter slab workers regarding the quality and value of hides and skins in Rubaya sub-county, Mbarara District. A cross-sectional design was employed using stratified random sampling, involving 109 respondents surveyed through structured questionnaires and observational checklists. Results indicated that farmers exhibited limited knowledge and poor attitudes towards hide and skin quality, with 54.8% unsure of income value, while slaughter slab workers demonstrated relatively better knowledge, with 81.3% recognizing industrial uses. Key factors contributing to defects included ectoparasite infestations, horn injuries, poor bleeding and carcass hoisting techniques, thorn scratches, barbed wire injuries, and skin diseases. The study recommends targeted training programs on improved animal husbandry and slaughter practices, development of a clear pricing and grading structure, and enhanced access to market and quality information to improve stakeholder attitudes and practices.

To Cite :

Ariho A, Twinamatsiko R, Mutagubya JP, Tumwine, G, Besigye SS, Namukomazi L., 2026. Knowledge, Attitudes And Practices of Livestock Farmers And Slaughter Slab Workers Regarding Hides And Skins Quality in Mbarara District, Uganda. Agriculture, Food, Environment and Animal Sciences, 7(1): 1-16. <https://doi.org/110.5281/zenodo.20365294>

INTRODUCTION

Hides and skins are valuable by-products of the livestock industry, serving as critical raw materials for the leather sector and contributing significantly to national export earnings. In Uganda, hides and skins generated over USD 146 million in 2020, making the leather industry the third-largest contributor to the country's agricultural exports (Nyangoma, 2021). Despite this economic potential, the sector continues to grapple with challenges related to the poor quality of hides and skins, largely attributed to factors such as poor animal husbandry, livestock diseases, ectoparasite infestations, inadequate slaughter techniques, and suboptimal post-slaughter handling (Eshetu et al., 2020; Gebrehiwot, 2017; Getabalew et al., 2021; Kahsay et al., 2015). Moreover, farmers' and butchers' knowledge, attitudes, and skills in handling hides and skins are often limited, which further contributes to defects and reduces economic value (Burgat, 2004; Maier et al., 2017). While previous studies provide insights at regional and national levels, there is limited information on localized, community-level practices and perceptions, which are crucial for designing effective interventions. Husen et al. (2016) and Kahsay et al. (2015) argue that more localized training and awareness programs are needed, but again, their work focused on broader regional assessments rather than on specific sub-county-level data. Understanding the current knowledge and perception of key stakeholders in the industry, including farmers and butchers at the local slaughter slabs, is crucial for understanding the challenges and opportunities in relation to the quality and value of hides and skins as they have a significant contribution to the country's export earnings (Jabbar, 2002). There remains a critical gap in localized, community-level assessment of stakeholders' knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP), especially at the sub-county level where day-to-day livestock production and slaughtering occur. Rubaya sub-county in Mbarara District is a livestock-intensive area with high cattle production and slaughter activity, yet no comprehensive study has assessed the KAP of stakeholders in this locality. Understanding how farmers and slaughter slab workers perceive, handle, and manage hides and skins at the grassroots level is essential for improving quality, enhancing economic returns, and informing targeted training programs. This study, therefore, aimed to assess the KAP of livestock farmers and slaughter slab workers regarding the quality and value of hides and skins in Rubaya sub-county, providing evidence to guide policy and extension services.

MATERIALS and METHODS

Ethical Approval

This study is a non-invasive, questionnaire-based cross-sectional survey and is exempt from formal ethics committee approval under institutional regulations of Makerere University. Administrative permission was obtained from the relevant local authorities on 18 December 2025, and informed consent was secured from all participants with full confidentiality ensured.

Selection of the Study Area

The study was conducted in Rubaya sub-county, Mbarara District, Uganda, specifically in the parishes of Itara, Bunenero, Ruburara, and Ruhunga. Rubaya sub-county is located between 0° 27'20" S and 30° 40'31" E in Kashari South County. The area was selected due to its high livestock population, including indigenous and crossbred cattle, goats, and sheep, which makes it a key site for assessing stakeholder knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to the quality and value of hides and skins.

Study Design and Sampling Frame

A descriptive cross-sectional study targeting livestock farmers and slaughter slab workers was conducted in Rubaya sub-county, Mbarara District. Both quantitative and qualitative approaches were employed to assess stakeholders' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding hides and skins. The study included small-scale and large-scale farmers of cattle, sheep, and goats, slaughter slab workers, and key informants, including local leaders, religious leaders, and extension workers.

Sample Selection and Sampling Technique

To determine the sample size, a simplified formula by Cochran (1977) was used, assuming a 95% confidence level, 5% precision, and a proportion of 93.4% from previous studies (Asegede et al., 2015), yielding a total of 109 respondents. A stratified random sampling approach was applied, with respondents proportionally allocated across the four selected parishes. Key informants KIIs were purposively selected with the assistance of local council leaders and included progressive dairy farmers, elder farmers, farmers' leaders, and livestock extension workers.

Data Collection

Quantitative data were collected using a standard structured questionnaire administered to a total of 109 respondents, comprising 93 livestock farmers and 16

slaughter slab workers, who were randomly selected from the four parishes of the study area. A list of farmers was prepared in consultation with local extension personnel and local leaders, and respondents were randomly sampled from this list across all four parishes. Farmers and slaughter slab workers were interviewed separately to ensure accurate and unbiased responses. For qualitative data, interview guides and observation checklists were used.

Data Quality Control

The data quality control involved the review of the research objectives and questions to ensure that data collection tools were aligned with them. Research tools were pretested to ensure the validity and reliability of the tools. A representative sample size consisting of eight livestock farmers and four slaughter slab workers was first selected from the area of the study for pretesting the data collection tools. The pretest data was analyzed to identify any issues with the data collection tools and based on the feedback received from the pretest participants and the analysis of the pretest data, the data collection tools were revised to address any issues that were identified.

Data Analysis

The collected data were extracted from the questionnaires and transferred into a Microsoft excel data sheet, exported to and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. Descriptive statistics were used and frequencies of the different study variables were computed and presented. Qualitative data collected through observations and key informant interviews were recorded in notebooks, analyzed, categorized and interpreted according to themes and patterns in line with the study objectives. The qualitative findings were then triangulated with survey data to provide a comprehensive understanding of factors influencing knowledge, attitudes, and practices, and to enrich the interpretation of quantitative results.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Social Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Among livestock farmers, the majority were male (69.9%) and married (92.5%). Most respondents (65.6%) were aged between 36–55 years. Regarding education level, nearly half (49.5%) had attained primary education, 29% had no formal education, 18.3% had secondary education, and only 3.2% had tertiary education. The majority (80.7%) had more than five years of experience in livestock production, indicating substantial practical exposure to animal management (Table 1). All the slaughter slab workers were male, and the majority of them were aged

between 36-55years (81.3%), with 68.8% married. Over half (56.3%) had attained primary education, and 50% had 5–10 years of working experience in slaughter operations.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the farmers

Variable	Response	Frequency (n=93)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Male	65	69.9
	Female	28	30.1
Age group	18-35yrs	8	8.60
	36-55yrs	61	65.6
	>55yrs	24	25.8
Marital status	Divorced	2	2.15
	Married	86	92.5
	Single	4	4.30
Level of education	None	27	29
	Primary	46	49.5
	Secondary	17	18.3
	Tertiary	3	3.2
Religion	Born again	3	3.23
	Catholic	36	38.7
	Moslem	2	2.15
	Protestant	18	19.3
	SDA	1	1.07
Occupation	Butcher	1	1.06
	Livestock farmer	93	98.9
Experience in livestock keeping	<5yrs	3	3.23
	5-10yrs	15	16.1
	11-15yrs	27	29
	16-20yrs	26	28
	>20yrs	22	21.5

Knowledge of Farmers on The Value and Quality of Hides And Skins

A large proportion (74.2%) strongly agreed that hides and skins are used as raw materials for footwear, belts, sutures, car seats, purses, and related products. Similarly, 57% strongly agreed that hides and skins are of great value in leather, fur, medical, textile, and craft applications. However, knowledge gaps were evident in certain areas. More than half of the farmers (54.8%) were not sure whether hides and skins serve as a source of income after sale. Additionally, 28% strongly disagreed that hides and skins reduce waste and environmental pollution, while 35.5% were uncertain about this environmental benefit. Knowledge of traditional uses was also mixed, with 32.3% indicating uncertainty (Table 2).

Table 2. Knowledge of farmers on the value of hides and skins

Variables	Strongly agree, (n=93) (%)	Agree, (n=93) (%)	Not sure, (n=93) (%)	Disagree, (n=93) (%)	Strongly disagree, (n=93) (%)
Knowledge on value of Hides and skins					
They are of importance to farmers	9.7	48.4	5.4	20.4	16.1
They are of great value in leather, fur, medical, textile, craft applications	57.0	38.7	3.2	-	1.1
Raw materials for foot ware, belts, sutures, car seats, purses, etc.	74.2	22.6	1.1	1.1	1.1
They are source of income after sales	5.4	10.8	54.8	19.4	9.7
Reduce waste and pollution as an environmental benefit	12.9	12.9	35.5	10.8	28.0
Various traditional uses	6.5	19.4	32.3	29.0	12.8

The majority of farmers identified ectoparasites such as ticks and mange (97.8%) and horn-related injuries (97.8%) as major contributors to defects in hides and skins. Animal diseases, particularly Lumpy Skin Disease (92.4%), and lack of knowledge regarding quality (94.6%) were also widely recognized as important factors (Table 3).

Table 3. Factors affecting the quality of hides and skins

Variable	Frequency (n=93)	Percentage (%)
Lack knowledge on quality of hides and skins	87	94.6
Breed of the animal	35	37.6
Feeding practices	44	47.3
Age of the animal	11	12
Environmental factors like thorny bushes	51	55.4
Animal diseases like LSD	85	92.4
Ectoparasites like ticks, mange	91	97.8
Damages from fellow animal horns	91	97.8
Improper branding	15	16.7
Poor knowledge on economic benefit	15	16.7

Knowledge of Slaughter Slab Workers on The Quality and Value of Hides and Skins

The majority of the slaughter slab workers strongly agreed that hides and skins are useful in leather, fur, medical, textile industries, and craft accessories (81.3%). Similarly, 68.8% strongly agreed that hides and skins are important to slaughter operations, and 75% strongly agreed that they are used in various manufactured products. However, 56.3% were unsure whether hides and skins represent an additional income source. A majority (75%) strongly agreed that hides and skins are used as food in some communities (Table 4).

Table 4. Knowledge of slaughter slab workers on the value of hides and skins

Variable	Strongly agree, (n=16) (%)	Agree, (n=16) (%)	Not sure, (=16) (%)	Disagree, (n=16) (%)	Strongly disagree, (n=16) (%)
Important to slaughter slab workers	68.8	31.3	–	–	–
Useful in leather, fur, medical, textile industry, craft and accessories	81.3	18.8	–	–	–
Used in foot ware, belts, sutures, car seat, purses, football, clothing	75	18.8	6.3	–	–
Source of additional income	18.8	18.8	56.3	6.1	–
Source of food to humans in some communities	75.0	12.5	12.5	–	–

All slaughter slab workers (100%) identified inadequate bleeding and improper carcass hoisting as major factors affecting quality. Pulling hides around tough or tight areas was reported by 87.5% of respondents. Delayed flaying and excessive knife use were each reported by 62.5% (Table 5).

Table 5. Factors affecting hides and skins quality (slaughter slab worker response)

Variable	Frequency (n=16)	Percentage (%)
Factors affecting skin and hides quality		
Less bleeding	16	100
Hoisting carcass	16	100
Delayed flaying after slaughter	10	62.5
Excessive knife work	12	62.5
Pulling of hides/skins around tough tight parts	14	87.5
Knowledge about quality and grading or quality assessment	12	75

Attitude of Farmers Towards The Quality and Value of Hides and Skins

While 59.1% agreed that hides and skins are useful by-products of the livestock industry, only 7.5% strongly agreed. Notably, 43.5% disagreed that they would take responsibility for the quality of hides and skins from their animals, and 20.7% strongly disagreed. Uncertainty was common: 43% were unsure whether quality knowledge would benefit both farmers and the leather industry, and 34.8% were unsure about uses beyond traditional applications.

However, training was widely viewed positively, with 31.2% strongly agreeing and 38.7% agreeing that training on animal handling would improve quality (Table 6).

Table 6. Attitude of farmers towards the quality of hides and skins

Variables	Strongly agree, (n=93) (%)	Agree, (n=93) (%)	Not sure, (n=93) (%)	Disagree, (n=93) (%)	Strongly disagree, (n=93) (%)
Useful by products in livestock industry	7.5	59.1	10.8	14.0	8.6
Good quality hides and skins is important part of my responsibility	18.3	12.9	23.7	34.4	10.8
Avoiding damage of hides during life time improves quality	12.9	30.1	31.2	16.1	9.7
Quality knowledge will be beneficial to leather industry and farmers as well	7.5	16.1	43.0	23.7	9.7
Good livestock practices husbandry practices can prevent damage	7.5	32.3	30.1	19.4	10.8
Take responsibility of quality hides and skins from your animals	3.3	16.3	16.3	43.5	20.7
Understand use of skins and hides beyond traditional use	6.5	16.3	34.8	25.0	17.4
maximizing the use of skins and hides is beneficial for economy development	5.4	11.8	28.0	29.0	25.8
Trainings on animal handling would improve the quality	31.2	38.7	21.5	6.5	2.2

Attitudes And Practices of Slaughter Slab Workers Towards The Quality And Value of Hides And Skins

Most of the respondents strongly agreed that good quality hides and skins benefit the leather industry (75%) and that production of quality hides is an important part of their responsibility (68.8%). Training was strongly supported, with 81.3% strongly agreeing that training would improve quality. However, misconceptions

were observed: 43.8% strongly disagreed that proper cleaning reduces contamination, indicating inconsistency in technical understanding (Table 7).

Table 7. Attitude of slaughter slab workers towards the quality and value of hides and skins

Variable	Strongly agree, (n=16) (%)	Agree, (n=16) (%)	Not sure, (n=16) (%)	Disagree, (n=16) (%)	Strongly disagree, (n=16) (%)
Attitude of slaughter slab workers to quality					
Production of good quality hides and skins is an important part	68.8	31.3	–	–	–
Good quality knowledge will be beneficial to my job operations	43.8	43.8	6.3	6.3	–
Good quality hides and skins is beneficial to leather industry	75.0	18.8	6.3	–	–
Believe use of recommended flaying tools reduces hides and skins defects	25.0	12.5	43.8	12.5	6.3
Proper cleaning of hides and skins reduces contamination	–	–	31.3	25.0	43.8
Believe use of unconventional flaying tools, beating of animals affects quality of hides	6.3	18.8	31.3	31.3	12.5
Training on animal handling and raw hides and skins to slaughter slab workers will improve quality	81.3	18.8	–	–	–

Practices of Farmers Regarding The Quality of Hides And Skins

Farmers reported widespread implementation of disease prevention practices. Vaccination (93%) and parasite control (93%) were highly reported. Clearing grazing areas (74.2%) and dehorning animals (72%) were also common practices (Table 8). However, only 4.3% reported continually seeking knowledge to improve quality. Additionally, 37.6% reported using sticks and whips during animal handling, which may contribute to skin damage.

Table 8. Practices of farmers that positively influence the quality of hides and skins

Variable	Frequency (n=93)	Percentage(%)
Dehorning of animals to reduce damage	67	72
vaccinating animals to reduce skin diseases	84	93
Clearing grazing areas to reduce thorns	69	74.2
Control parasites like ticks, mange	84	93
Use of sticks and whips when looking after animals	35	37.6
Apply brands out of the butt area	0	0
Continually seek knowledge to improve quality	4	4.3

Slaughter slab workers reported high adherence to certain quality-related practices. All respondents (100%) reported cleaning hides with sufficient water and using slaughter methods that facilitate bleeding. Carcass hoisting and slanting floors were universally practiced. Most (81.3%) made ripping lines before flaying and inspected hides for defects. Seeking buyer feedback was common (93.8%). However, only 50% reported using recommended flaying tools, and 31.3% used appropriate preservation methods such as salting (Table 9).

Table 9. Practices of slaughter slab workers that positively influence the quality of hides and skins

Variable	Frequency (n=16)	Percentage(%)
Practices of slaughter slab workers		
Starving animals 24hrs before slaughter, providing water only to reduce lumen content	3	18.8
Cleaning hides and skins with clean and enough water after slaughter	16	100
Use of appropriate preservation methods like salting	5	31.3
Gentle falling of animals during slaughter	11	68.8
use of traditional slaughter method	7	43.8
Use Islamic/Rabbinic slaughter method	16	100
Hoisting the carcass or use of slanting floor is done to facilitate bleeding	16	100
Ripping lines must be made before flaying proceeds	13	81.3
Regularly inspect hides and skins for any signs of damage or defects	13	81.3
Proactive in seeking professional assistance and guidance for hides and skins preservation	8	50
Keep updated on the market trends of hides and skin	13	81.3
Seek feedback from buyers on the quality of the hides and skins	15	93.8
Use recommended flaying tools ie hard sharp pointed knife, hard short curved knife	8	50

Common defects of hides and skins observed at farm level Common defects included scratches from barbed wire (96.8%), external parasites (91.4%), and skin diseases (92.4%).

Major challenges reported by farmers included livestock diseases and parasites (96.7%), insufficient knowledge on animal handling (91.4%), and difficulty handling animals without causing damage (92.5%) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Common defects of hides and skins and challenges faced in livestock industry

Challenges Faced by Slaughter Slab Workers In Maintaining Quality of Hides And Skins

All slaughter slab workers (100%) reported insufficient training and limited access to water and cleaning facilities as major challenges. Limited storage facilities (93.8%) and difficulty handling hides without causing damage (81.3%) were also common.

Tabel 10. Challenges faced by slaughter slab workers in maintaining the quality of hides and skins

Variable	Frequency (n=16)	Percentage (%)
Challenges faced by slaughter slab workers		
Insufficient training on quality	16	100
limited access to water and cleaning facilities	16	100
limited storage facilities	15	93.8
Availability of necessary tools and equipment	10	62.5
Contamination of hides and skins during slaughter slab operations	9	56.3
Difficulty in handling hides and skins without causing damage	13	81.3

DISCUSSION

This study revealed that livestock farmers had low knowledge regarding the economic value and quality importance of hides and skins. A small proportion recognized hides and skins as a direct source of income, and many perceived them as by-products that primarily benefit traders rather than producers. The study indicated that these farmers believe that the hides are used for other products but are not directly useful to them. They only end at the point of selling the live animals to the traders who do not pay any extra money for these hides/skins, and thus believe they never directly benefit from them. This could be attributed to the illiteracy levels of farmers, since they could not access and read the available information in this field. In contrast, slaughter slab workers demonstrated relatively better knowledge of the usefulness and market value of hides and skins. These findings are consistent with Lumarai (2023), who reported that farmers often lack knowledge about the value of hides and skins, viewing them primarily as raw materials for leather products rather than a direct source of income. Similarly, Gebrehiwot (2017) and Asegede et al. (2015) documented inadequate knowledge among value chain actors concerning quality standards and marketing systems. Assefa and Kuma (2016) further observed that insufficient knowledge of proper handling and flaying techniques contributes significantly to defects. The relatively better knowledge observed among slaughter slab workers may be attributed to their closer involvement in post-slaughter processing activities. It could also be related to the fact that these slaughter slab workers had attained awareness of the importance of hides and skins.

Farmers generally exhibited poor attitudes toward the responsibility of producing quality hides and skins. Many did not strongly believe that hide quality was part of their role in livestock production. In contrast, slaughter slab workers showed more positive attitudes, acknowledging that good-quality hides benefit both the

leather industry and their livelihoods. These findings align with Gebrehiwot (2017), Getabalew et al. (2021) and Skunmun (2013), who reported negative attitudes among farmers toward hide and skin quality management. Previous studies suggest that limited awareness and absence of price incentives reduce motivation to maintain quality (Getabalew et al., 2021). The better attitude among slaughter slab workers may reflect greater exposure to market requirements and quality grading systems. The findings seem to indicate that information is delivered to the slaughter places and not to the farmers who are the backbone of livestock management, and hence their ignorance of the quality would affect the industry greatly.

At farm level, the study identified ectoparasites, skin diseases (including Lumpy Skin Disease), horn damage, and scratches from barbed wire and thorns as major causes of defects. Practices such as prodding animals with sticks and poor grazing management also contributed to hide damage. At slaughter level, defects were associated with improper bleeding, carcass handling, flay cuts, inadequate sanitation, and use of crude tools. This could be attributed to the system of grazing where animals are left to move freely, getting exposed to ticks, diseases and fights amongst themselves. The majority of cattle in the region are long-horned, and hence can easily damage the hides. These findings are consistent with Getabalew et al. (2021), and Koloka and Moreki (2010), who identified parasites and mechanical damage as key pre-slaughter factors affecting hides and skins. Kebede (2013) reported substantial skin rejection rates of up to 56% due to ectoparasites. Studies have also documented scratches, wounds, and parasitic damage as major pre-slaughter defects (Husen et al., 2016; Kahsay et al., 2015). Post-slaughter defects such as flay cuts, putrefaction, and improper preservation have similarly been reported by (Ebrahiem et al., 2015; Husen et al., 2016; Ochama, 2016). These defects significantly reduce grading scores and economic returns (Alemnesh et al., 2018; Wanyoike et al., 2018).

Slaughter slab workers further reported infrastructural and operational challenges, including limited training, inadequate access to clean water, poor storage facilities, and lack of advanced techniques. They relied solely on locally acquired knowledge for slaughtering and handling hides, lacking advanced techniques to maintain quality, which may be linked to the fact that the majority had not attained higher education. Similar infrastructural and knowledge constraints were reported by Adem (2019) and Asegede et al. (2015). The production of high-quality hides and skins faces numerous challenges, including livestock diseases and parasites, insufficient knowledge of animal handling, and difficulty maintaining animals without damage (Adem, 2019; Getabalew et al., 2021). These issues, along with poor slaughter operations and inadequate preservation techniques, significantly impact hide and skin quality (Gebrehiwot, 2017; Getabalew et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that farmers possess limited knowledge and exhibit poor attitudes toward hide and skin quality, which negatively influence production practices. Slaughter slab workers show relatively better knowledge and attitudes but face infrastructural and technical limitations that affect quality preservation.

Improving hide and skin quality requires targeted training for both farmers and slaughter slab workers, enhanced awareness of economic benefits, improved slaughter infrastructure, and implementation of transparent grading and pricing systems. Strengthening extension services and promoting appropriate animal husbandry and handling practices will be critical to reducing defects and enhancing the competitiveness of the leather sector.

Study Limitations

This study was descriptive in nature. The relatively small number of slaughter slab workers (n=16) limited the scope for inferential statistical comparisons. As such, findings should be interpreted as indicative patterns rather than statistically generalized conclusions. Future research with larger and more balanced samples could further examine determinants of KAP using multivariable analytical approaches.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have declared that there are no competing interests.

Author' Contribution

All authors made a significant contribution to the work reported, whether in the conception, study design, execution, acquisition of data, analysis and interpretation or in all these areas; took part in drafting, revising or critically reviewing the article; gave final approval of the version to be published; have agreed on the journal to which the article has been submitted; and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

REFERENCES

Adem M., 2019. Production of hide and skin in Ethiopia; marketing opportunities and constraints: A review paper. *Cogent Food & Agriculture*, 5(1): 1565078. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311932.2019.1565078>

Alemnesh B, Getachew T, Tariku J., 2018. Assessment of quality and marketing of hide and skin in Adamitulu Jidokombolcha and Bora Woreda in East Shewa Zone

of Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Livestock Production*, 9(10): 269-279. <https://doi.org/10.5897/IJLP2017.0372>

Assefa F, Kuma A., 2016. Assessment of the status of hides and skins production, opportunities and constraints in Wolaita Zone, southern Ethiopia. *Assessment*, 53.

Burgat F., 2004. Non-violence towards animals in the thinking of Gandhi: The problem of animal husbandry. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*, 17(3): 223-248. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:JAGE.0000033082.58743.5b>

Cochran WG., 1977. *Sampling techniques*. John Wiley & Sons.

Ebrahiem MA, Ali M, Turki I, Haroun H, Bushara I, Mekki D., 2015. Defects and grading of hides and skins in Kordofan region, Sudan.

Eshetu M, Bekele E, Tadesse Y., 2020. Pre-and post-slaughter factors influencing hide and skin quality in west shewa zone, Ethiopia. *Open Journal of Animal Sciences*, 10(01): 162-181. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojas.2020.101009>

Gebrehiwot T., 2017. Hides And Skins Production And Marketing Systems In Ethiopia; A Systematic Review (Des, 2017). *International Journal of Engineering Development and Research*, 5(4): 1125-1128-1125-1128. <https://rjwave.org/IJEDR/papers/IJEDR1704181.pdf>

Getabalew M, Mindaye A, Zewdie D., 2021. Hide and Skin Quality Factors and Marketing Systems in Ethiopia: A Review. *Developing Country Studies*, 11(6).

Husen A, Tilahun A, Teshale A, Gashaw T., 2016. Review on pre and post-slaughter defects of hide and skin in Ethiopia. *Advances in Biological Research*, 10(3): 154-161.

Jabbar MA., 2002. Livestock and hides and skins marketing in Kenya: Problems and investment needs.

Kahsay T, Negash G, Hagos Y, Hadush B., 2015. Pre-slaughter, slaughter and post-slaughter defects of skins and hides at the Sheba Tannery and Leather Industry, Tigray region, northern Ethiopia. *Onderstepoort Journal of Veterinary Research*, 82(1): 1-7. <http://www.ojvr.org/index.php/ojvr/article/view/931/html>

Kebede M., 2013. Effect of small ruminant ectoparasites in the tanning industry in Ethiopia: a review. *Journal of Animal science advances*, 3: 424-430.

Koloka O, Moreki J., 2010. Performance of hides and skins subsector in Botswana: A critical review. *Livestock Research for Rural Development*, 22: 150-175. <http://www.lrrd.org/lrrd22/5/kolo22090.html>

Lumarai R., 2023. Effect of small-scale hides and skin business on trader's income in Nakuru County, Kenya Egerton University.

Maier M, Oelbermann AL, Renner M, Weidner E., 2017. Screening of European medicinal herbs on their tannin content—New potential tanning agents for the leather industry. *Industrial crops and products*, 99: 19-26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2017.01.033>

Asegede MA, Bsrat AB, Hagos YH, Gugsu GG., 2015. Livestock market value chain assessment in selected sites of Tigray, north Ethiopia: challenges and opportunities for enhancing animal product export. [http://www.idosi.org/gv/gv14\(1\)15/7.pdf](http://www.idosi.org/gv/gv14(1)15/7.pdf)

Nyangoma J., 2021. Data dissemination by Uganda Bureau of Statistics. *IASSIST Quarterly*, 45(3-4). <https://doi.org/10.29173/iq991>

Ochama J., 2016. Comparison of defects on hides and skins during slaughter, preservation and storage at Lugazi municipal slaughter slab, Buikwe district and Tororo municipal abattoir, Tororo District Busitema University.

Skunmun P., 2013. *Thai Leather: Quality Cattle Hides in Thailand*. Thaksin University Press.

Wanyoike FN, Mugunieri LG, Mtimet N, Kiptoo E, Gulaid I., 2018. An analysis of the hides and skins value chain in Somaliland. ILRI Research Report 50. Nairobi, Kenya: International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI).